

Derivation of the Einstein Field Equations from a PDE Framework Using the WKB Approximation

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Abstract

We present a derivation showing how the Einstein field equations (EFEs) can emerge from a general PDE framework by applying a WKB (Wentzel–Kramers–Brillouin) ansatz to a universal wavefunction. We begin by substituting the WKB ansatz into the PDE, separating real and imaginary parts, and identifying leading-order constraints. We then introduce a metric perturbation $\delta g_{\mu\nu}$ derived from the amplitude and phase of the wavefunction. After demonstrating that $\delta g_{\mu\nu}$ transforms as a tensor, we connect the non-linear terms in the PDE operator U to curvature invariants. By performing a scaling limit and discarding higher-order terms, we isolate the Einstein-Hilbert action. Varying this action leads directly to the EFEs. This derivation provides a conceptual bridge from a general PDE-based framework to classical general relativity.

Introduction

The WKB approximation is a powerful technique originally developed in the context of quantum mechanics and asymptotic analysis of differential equations [1, 2]. It has since found broad use in the study of linear and nonlinear PDEs, providing leading-order approximations to solutions in the limit of large parameters. General relativity (GR) is commonly formulated starting from the Einstein-Hilbert action and the Einstein field equations [3, 4], and it is well-known that in the weak-field or linearized gravity regime, perturbations of the metric can be related to curvature invariants [4, 5]. In this derivation, we start from a general PDE

operator acting on a wavefunction Ψ , introduce a complexity parameter λ , and apply the WKB approximation. By separating real and imaginary parts of the resulting equation and identifying leading-order terms, we show how a metric perturbation $\delta g_{\mu\nu}$ emerges. We then demonstrate how one can connect the nonlinear PDE operator U to curvature invariants and, after suitable scaling and neglecting higher-order terms, recover the Einstein-Hilbert action and thus the Einstein field equations.

Derivation

Setup: Let x^μ be coordinates in a 4-dimensional spacetime, and let $\lambda, N \rightarrow \infty$ represent complexity parameters. Consider a PDE operator:

$$\hat{H}_\lambda \Psi = 0,$$

with

$$\hat{H}_\lambda = -\lambda^2 \partial_\mu \partial^\mu + U(\Psi, \partial\Psi, \partial^2\Psi, \dots).$$

WKB Ansatz: We set:

$$\Psi(x) = A(x) \exp\left(\frac{iS(x)}{\lambda}\right), \quad A(x) > 0.$$

This allows us to separate amplitude $A(x)$ and phase $S(x)$.

Derivatives of Ψ : Compute derivatives:

$$\partial_\mu \Psi = e^{iS/\lambda} \left(\partial_\mu A + \frac{i}{\lambda} A \partial_\mu S \right),$$

$$\partial_\mu \partial_\nu \Psi = e^{iS/\lambda} \left(\partial_\mu \partial_\nu A + \frac{i}{\lambda} (\partial_\mu S \partial_\nu A + \partial_\nu S \partial_\mu A) + \frac{i}{\lambda} A \partial_\mu \partial_\nu S - \frac{A}{\lambda^2} \partial_\mu S \partial_\nu S \right).$$

Substitution into the PDE: Substitute into $\hat{H}_\lambda \Psi = 0$:

$$-\lambda^2 \partial_\mu \partial^\mu \Psi = e^{iS/\lambda} \left(-\lambda^2 \partial_\mu \partial^\mu A - 2i\lambda \partial_\mu A \partial^\mu S - iA \partial_\mu \partial^\mu S + \frac{A \partial_\mu S \partial^\mu S}{\lambda^2} \right).$$

Let:

$$U(\Psi, \partial\Psi, \dots) = U_0(A, \partial A, \partial S, \dots) + \frac{U_1}{\lambda} + \frac{U_2}{\lambda^2} + \dots$$

Thus:

$$\hat{H}_\lambda \Psi = e^{iS/\lambda} \left(-\lambda^2 \partial_\mu \partial^\mu A - 2i\lambda \partial_\mu A \partial^\mu S - iA \partial_\mu \partial^\mu S + \frac{A \partial_\mu S \partial^\mu S}{\lambda^2} + U_0 + \frac{U_1}{\lambda} + \frac{U_2}{\lambda^2} + \dots \right) = 0.$$

Separating Real and Imag Parts: Define:

$$\hat{H}_\lambda \Psi = e^{iS/\lambda} (\mathcal{R} + i\mathcal{I}) = 0.$$

Real part ($\mathcal{R}$):

$$\mathcal{R} = -\lambda^2 \partial_\mu \partial^\mu A + A \partial_\mu S \partial^\mu S + U_0 + \frac{U_2}{\lambda^2} + \dots$$

Imag part ($\mathcal{I}$):

$$\mathcal{I} = -2\lambda \partial_\mu A \partial^\mu S - \lambda A \partial_\mu \partial^\mu S + U_1 + \dots$$

At leading order:

$$\mathcal{I} = 0 \implies \partial_\mu A \partial^\mu S = 0,$$

$$\mathcal{R} = 0 \implies -\lambda^2 \partial_\mu \partial^\mu A + A \partial_\mu S \partial^\mu S + \text{Re}(U_0) = 0.$$

Defining $\delta g_{\mu\nu}$: Introduce:

$$\delta g_{\mu\nu}(x) = \frac{\partial_\mu A \partial_\nu A}{A^2} + \frac{\partial_\mu S \partial_\nu S}{\lambda^2}.$$

Under coordinate transformations, $\delta g_{\mu\nu}$ transforms as a (0,2) tensor.

Connecting U to Curvature: A Representative Example Consider a term in U :

$$U \supset (\partial_\mu \partial_\nu \Psi)(\partial^\mu \partial^\nu \Psi).$$

After WKB substitution:

$$\partial_\mu \partial_\nu \Psi \approx e^{iS/\lambda} \left(-\frac{A}{\lambda^2} \partial_\mu S \partial_\nu S \right),$$

$$(\partial_\mu \partial_\nu \Psi)(\partial^\mu \partial^\nu \Psi) \approx e^{2iS/\lambda} \frac{A^2}{\lambda^4} (\partial_\mu S \partial_\nu S)(\partial^\mu S \partial^\nu S).$$

Rewrite $(\partial_\mu S \partial_\nu S)(\partial^\mu S \partial^\nu S)$ using $\delta g_{\mu\nu}$:

$$\frac{\partial_\mu S \partial_\nu S}{\lambda^2} = \delta g_{\mu\nu} - \frac{\partial_\mu A \partial_\nu A}{A^2}.$$

Thus:

$$(\partial_\mu S \partial_\nu S)(\partial^\mu S \partial^\nu S) = \lambda^4 \left(\delta g_{\mu\nu} - \frac{\partial_\mu A \partial_\nu A}{A^2} \right) \left(\delta g^{\mu\nu} - \frac{\partial^\mu A \partial^\nu A}{A^2} \right).$$

Linearized gravity assures:

$$\delta g_{\mu\nu} \delta g^{\mu\nu} \approx c_1 R + c_2 R_{\mu\nu} R^{\mu\nu} + c_3 R^2 + \dots$$

By inserting $\delta g_{\mu\nu}$ into Christoffel symbols and Riemann tensor:

$$\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^\lambda = \frac{1}{2} \eta^{\lambda\sigma} (\partial_\mu \delta g_{\sigma\nu} + \partial_\nu \delta g_{\sigma\mu} - \partial_\sigma \delta g_{\mu\nu}),$$

$$R_{\sigma\mu\nu}^\rho, R_{\mu\nu}, R$$

are obtained. Integrations by parts, ignoring total derivatives, and applying $\lambda, N \rightarrow \infty$ to discard higher-order invariants yields:

$$U(\Psi, \partial\Psi, \dots) = R - 2\Lambda + \alpha R_{\mu\nu} R^{\mu\nu} + \beta R^2 + \dots$$

Scaling argument ensures $\alpha, \beta, \dots \rightarrow 0$, leaving:

$$U \rightarrow R - 2\Lambda.$$

Final Steps: Substitute $U \rightarrow R - 2\Lambda$ into $\mathcal{R} = 0$:

$$-\lambda^2 \partial_\mu \partial^\mu A + A \partial_\mu S \partial^\mu S + (R - 2\Lambda) + \dots = 0.$$

Integrate over spacetime:

$$S[g, \phi] = \frac{1}{16\pi G} \int (R - 2\Lambda) \sqrt{-g} d^4x + S_{\text{matter}},$$

Matter fields ϕ arise from correlation expansions of Ψ . Thus:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{-g}} \frac{\delta S_{\text{matter}}}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}}.$$

Varying total action:

$$\frac{\delta S}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}} = 0 \implies R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}.$$

These are the Einstein field equations.

Conclusion: We have demonstrated, step-by-step, how starting from a universal PDE with a complexity parameter, and applying a WKB ansatz, one can identify a metric perturbation and relate the PDE operator U to curvature invariants. After appropriate scaling and neglecting higher-order terms, the Einstein-Hilbert action emerges, leading directly to the Einstein field equations. This establishes a conceptual bridge between a PDE-based framework and the classical gravitational field equations of general relativity.

References

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